

TOPIC: (data science)

Refined by: **DOCUMENT TYPES:** (ARTICLE OR REVIEW OR BOOK OR CLINICAL TRIAL OR CASE REPORT) AND **RESEARCH AREAS:** (BIOCHEMISTRY MOLECULAR BIOLOGY OR NUTRITION DIETETICS OR PHARMACOLOGY PHARMACY OR GASTROENTEROLOGY HEPATOLOGY OR PUBLIC ENVIRONMENTAL OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH OR GENETICS HEREDITY OR MEDICAL INFORMATICS OR MICROBIOLOGY OR SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY OTHER TOPICS OR CHEMISTRY OR NEUROSCIENCES NEUROLOGY OR LIFE SCIENCES BIOMEDICINE OTHER TOPICS OR BIOTECHNOLOGY APPLIED MICROBIOLOGY OR IMMUNOLOGY OR OPHTHALMOLOGY OR GERIATRICS GERONTOLOGY OR ANATOMY MORPHOLOGY OR PEDIATRICS OR OBSTETRICS GYNECOLOGY OR MICROSCOPY OR HEALTH CARE SCIENCES SERVICES OR DENTISTRY ORAL SURGERY MEDICINE OR CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM CARDIOLOGY OR UROLOGY NEPHROLOGY OR PATHOLOGY OR PARASITOLOGY OR ONCOLOGY OR ENDOCRINOLOGY METABOLISM OR PHYSIOLOGY OR PSYCHOLOGY OR DEVELOPMENTAL BIOLOGY OR RHEUMATOLOGY OR INFECTIOUS DISEASES OR ORTHOPEDICS OR RESEARCH EXPERIMENTAL MEDICINE OR DERMATOLOGY OR OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY OR HEMATOLOGY OR REHABILITATION OR TOXICOLOGY OR MATHEMATICAL COMPUTATIONAL BIOLOGY OR ANESTHESIOLOGY OR SURGERY OR ALLERGY OR CELL BIOLOGY OR GENERAL INTERNAL MEDICINE OR VIROLOGY OR RADIOLOGY NUCLEAR MEDICINE MEDICAL IMAGING OR REPRODUCTIVE BIOLOGY OR CRITICAL CARE MEDICINE OR PSYCHIATRY OR EVOLUTIONARY BIOLOGY OR MEDICAL LABORATORY TECHNOLOGY OR RESPIRATORY SYSTEM) AND **COUNTRIES/REGIONS:** (ENGLAND OR UK)

Timespan: All years. Databases: WOS, CCC, DIIDW, KJD, MEDLINE, RSCI, SCIELO.

Search language=Auto

TOPIC: (big data)

Refined by: **DOCUMENT TYPES:** (ARTICLE OR CASE REPORT OR BOOK OR CLINICAL TRIAL OR REPORT) AND **RESEARCH AREAS:** (EVOLUTIONARY BIOLOGY OR PSYCHIATRY OR GERIATRICS GERONTOLOGY OR GASTROENTEROLOGY HEPATOLOGY OR BIODIVERSITY CONSERVATION OR HEALTH CARE SCIENCES SERVICES OR RADIOLOGY NUCLEAR MEDICINE MEDICAL IMAGING OR BIOCHEMISTRY MOLECULAR BIOLOGY OR PSYCHOLOGY OR MEDICAL LABORATORY TECHNOLOGY OR INFECTIOUS DISEASES OR RESPIRATORY SYSTEM OR ONCOLOGY OR GENETICS HEREDITY OR DEVELOPMENTAL BIOLOGY OR PUBLIC ENVIRONMENTAL OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH OR TOXICOLOGY OR HEMATOLOGY OR PATHOLOGY OR OBSTETRICS GYNECOLOGY OR IMMUNOLOGY OR CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM CARDIOLOGY OR PHARMACOLOGY PHARMACY OR CELL BIOLOGY OR OPTICS OR NEUROSCIENCES NEUROLOGY OR REPRODUCTIVE BIOLOGY OR LIFE SCIENCES BIOMEDICINE OTHER TOPICS OR NUTRITION DIETETICS OR RESEARCH EXPERIMENTAL MEDICINE OR ORTHOPEDICS OR ENDOCRINOLOGY METABOLISM OR UROLOGY NEPHROLOGY OR PEDIATRICS OR ANATOMY MORPHOLOGY OR DERMATOLOGY OR SURGERY OR NURSING OR MICROBIOLOGY OR PHYSIOLOGY OR BIOTECHNOLOGY APPLIED MICROBIOLOGY OR GENERAL INTERNAL MEDICINE OR DENTISTRY ORAL SURGERY MEDICINE OR MEDICAL INFORMATICS)

Timespan: All years. Databases: WOS, CCC, DIIDW, KJD, MEDLINE, RSCI, SCIELO.

Search language=Auto

TOPIC: (cloud computing)

Refined by: **DOCUMENT TYPES:** (CLINICAL TRIAL OR ARTICLE OR BOOK OR REVIEW OR CASE REPORT) AND **RESEARCH AREAS:** (ANATOMY MORPHOLOGY OR SURGERY OR PHARMACOLOGY PHARMACY OR LIFE SCIENCES BIOMEDICINE OTHER TOPICS OR LEGAL MEDICINE OR ONCOLOGY OR PATHOLOGY OR BIOCHEMISTRY MOLECULAR BIOLOGY OR CELL BIOLOGY OR GENETICS HEREDITY OR MATHEMATICAL COMPUTATIONAL BIOLOGY OR MEDICAL ETHICS OR BIODIVERSITY CONSERVATION OR RESPIRATORY SYSTEM OR NEUROSCIENCES NEUROLOGY OR BIOTECHNOLOGY APPLIED MICROBIOLOGY OR TOXICOLOGY OR OPTICS OR MICROBIOLOGY OR GERIATRICS GERONTOLOGY OR PEDIATRICS OR INFECTIOUS DISEASES OR PUBLIC ENVIRONMENTAL OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH OR ORTHOPEDICS OR PSYCHOLOGY OR IMMUNOLOGY OR OPHTHALMOLOGY OR HEMATOLOGY OR MEDICAL LABORATORY TECHNOLOGY OR CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM CARDIOLOGY OR PSYCHIATRY OR GENERAL INTERNAL MEDICINE OR GASTROENTEROLOGY HEPATOLOGY OR RADIOLOGY NUCLEAR MEDICINE MEDICAL IMAGING OR PHYSIOLOGY OR ENDOCRINOLOGY METABOLISM OR HEALTH CARE SCIENCES SERVICES OR MICROSCOPY OR MEDICAL INFORMATICS OR DENTISTRY ORAL SURGERY MEDICINE OR RESEARCH EXPERIMENTAL MEDICINE OR EVOLUTIONARY BIOLOGY)

Timespan: All years. Databases: WOS, CCC, DIIDW, KJD, MEDLINE, RSCI, SCIELO.

Search language=Auto